

The Effect of Window Shopping Learning Model and Learning Motivation on Pancasila Education Learning Achievement at SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan

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ABSTRACT: Students in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan who lack high learning motivation will have more influence on the level of capture of the subject matter presented by the teacher to carry out learning tasks more effectively so as to improve their learning achievement. Less than optimal student learning achievement requires student motivation in choosing the model to be applied in the learning process in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan. The learning model applied in learning Pancasila Education is Window Shopping or Science Shopping, where with this model students will be enthusiastic and more active and motivated in actively following Pancasila Education learning, so that it is hoped that learning achievement can increase. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of Window Shopping learning model and learning motivation on learning achievement of students of SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan, Magetan Regency. This study uses quantitative methods with multiple linear regression analysis techniques. The results of this study concluded that there was a significant influence of the Windows Shopping learning model variables and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement both partially and simultaneously.

KEYWORDS: Learning Model, Windows Shopping, Learning Motivation, Learning Achievement

INTRODUCTION

The learning process experienced by seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan is a process of behavioural change carried out by students as a result of interaction with their environment in meeting their life needs, but in the development of Pancasila education learning while at school the teacher plays a major role in delivering material in class. Based on observations in Class VII Pancasila Education subjects, it is known that in general the learning process in the classroom using conventional learning, namely: lectures,

questions and answers, and assignments, students only receive, hear, and record explanations conveyed by the teacher. The use of media is limited to videos and power points. In addition, some students work on problems only looking for the final result of the problem in accordance with the theory and description of the material and are less able to explain the results of their analysis or based on their thoughts. This can be seen during the daily test as an evaluation of the results of material delivery, the average student score is only 64.5 with 32 students in one class observed. These results make concerns about the impact of the lack of student learning achievement.

The problem at SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan is that learning achievement is closely related to learning. Factors that affect learning achievement can come from within (internal) individuals and from outside (external) individuals who are influenced by factors from within the individual, consisting of physiological and psychological factors. Physiological factors are physical conditions and conditions of the five senses, while psychological factors are talent, interest, intelligence, achievement motivation, and cognitive abilities. Other factors, namely from outside the individual, consist of environmental factors and instrumental factors. Environmental factors are the social environment and natural environment, while instrumental factors are curriculum, materials, teachers, facilities, administration, and management (Purwanto, 2010).

While Syah (2012) also divides the factors that affect learning achievement into three types, namely:

1) Internal factors, including the physical and spiritual state of students, 2) External factors are the environmental conditions around students.

3) The learning approach factor, is a type of student learning effort that includes strategies and methods used by students to study subject matter.

In overcoming these problems, one of the efforts he made was to make learning variations in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan, namely by using approaches, models or learning methods that are different from what is usually done at the school, namely conventional learning whose learning activities are still dominated by the role of educators. Therefore, an appropriate approach,

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model, or model of learning is needed so that it is expected that learning becomes more meaningful, which involves the activeness of students so that students feel pleasant learning and make students more motivated to deepen their ability to absorb learning material.

An important aspect that influences the learning process is motivation (Soekamto and Winataputra, 1997).. This is because learning motivation plays an important role in providing passion and enthusiasm in learning, so that students who have high motivation will have strong energy to learn. In addition, motivation will provide a clear direction in learning activities, so that students who have high motivation will have two solid wings to reach the heights of achievement, namely energy wings and goal wings (Winkel, 1996). (Winkel, 1996).

According to Slameto, (2020), learning motivation is influenced by three components, namely:

- 1) Cognitive drive, which is the need to know, understand, and solve problems. This drive arises in the process of interaction between the student and the task/problem.
- 2) Self-esteem, that is, there are certain students who study hard and carry out tasks not primarily to gain knowledge or skills, but to gain status and self-esteem.
- 3) Affiliation needs, namely the need to master the subject / learning material with the intention of getting justification from others / friends. This need is difficult to separate from self-esteem.

Students in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan who lack high learning motivation will have more influence on the level of capture of the subject matter presented by the teacher to carry out learning tasks more effectively so as to improve their learning achievement. Less than optimal student learning achievement requires student motivation in choosing the model to be applied in the learning process in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan. The learning model applied in learning Pancasila Education is *Window Shopping* or Science Shopping, where with this model students will be enthusiastic and more active and motivated in actively following Pancasila Education learning, so that it is hoped that learning achievement can increase.

Moving on from the findings of the above problems, the author has various options in overcoming these problems. Actually, there is nothing wrong with conventional lecture- based learning, but today's students who are gen Z prefer things that are technological. Stillman's research (2017) suggests that generation Z is the latest working generation, born between 1995 and 2012, called the internet generation. In accordance with this research, generation Z is different from generation Y or millennials. In his book Stillman (2017) *How the Next Generation Is Transforming the Workplace* explained the differences, one of the differences between gen Y and gen Z is that generation Z masters technology more advanced, more open-minded and less concerned with norms. After understanding the meaning of the students studied from generation Z, it would be nice if teachers can also adjust learning options with methods according to their generation. The choice of learning methods can include using learning video media, online quiz media such as quizz kahot and, utilisation of social media, and cooperative learning media.

From several choices of learning models, it is expected that teachers play a role and try to be creative in the learning process that makes student learning fun, fosters interest and motivation, is active and reduces boredom. One of them is by using a method approach or learning model that is different from what is usually done at school with the hope that learning becomes more meaningful, involves student activities so that students feel fun in learning Pancasila Education. There is one learning model that can be used, namely the cooperative learning model, this model is a learning model where students learn in groups that have different levels of ability. One model that encourages students' active participation in the group is the *Window Shopping* learning model. This learning model is a group work- based learning model by going around to see the work of other groups to broaden their horizons. (Revianto, 2021).

Students who have learning motivation will have more influence on the level of capture of the subject matter presented by the teacher to carry out more effective learning tasks. The motivation that exists in students will develop further, if they can receive learning well and have a high sense of curiosity. Based on this background, the author is interested in conducting research with the title "The Effect of Window Shopping Learning Model and Learning Motivation on Pancasila Education Learning Achievement at SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan".

METHODS

This research will be conducted at SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Magetan, East Java. The research will be conducted in the 2023/2024 academic year, during the mid-semester to the end of the odd semester. This research uses quantitative methods. The population used was all seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Magetan with a total of 32 students. The sampling technique used is nonprobability sampling with the technique taken is saturated sampling.

Data collection techniques using documentation, questionnaires and observation techniques. Data analysis techniques used multiple linear regression which includes the instrument test stage, assumption test and hypothesis testing...

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis Result

1. Research Instrument Test Results

a. Data Validity Test

A data needs to be measured first to find out how valid the data is. The validity test is carried out to test the validity of research data. According to Sugiyono (2017) validity is the degree of accuracy between the data that occurs in the research object and the power reported by the researcher. After the calculation is done, then the result of the calculation, namely r_{hitung} , is compared with r_{tabel} with a significance level of 5% (α). If $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$ then the item is said to be valid, if $r_{hitung} \leq r_{tabel}$ then the item is said to be invalid.

Based on the results of the validity test for 42 question items, all items have been distributed to 30 respondents with the result that they are declared Valid and suitable for further data testing.

b. Data Reliability Test

Reliability test is used to determine the determination of research data. According to Sugiyono (2017) reliability means trustworthy, reliable. In this study, the data was obtained in the form of a questionnaire or questionnaire so that the formula used to conduct the reliability test.

The reliability test is carried out after the validity test and the test is a statement or question that is already valid. *Cronbach's alpha* which is between 0.50 - 0.60. In this study, researchers chose 0.60 as the reliability coefficient. The criteria for reliability testing are if the *Cronbach's alpha* value $\alpha > 0.60$ then the instrument has good reliability in other words the instrument is reliable or reliable. Meanwhile, if the *Cronbach's alpha* value < 0.60 then the instrument being tested is not reliable or reliable (Sugiyono, 2017).

Based on the results of the reliability test for 42 question items, all items have been distributed to 30 respondents with a value of 0.750 which means that these results are declared reliable or reliable and suitable for further data testing.

2. Prerequisite Assumption Test Results

a. Normality Test

Ghozali (2017) states that the normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution. A regression model that is considered good is to have a normal or near normal distribution. Descriptively, the normality test can be done using a standardised residual regression histogram. Before hypothesis testing is carried out, a data normality test is carried out. The normality test is used to determine whether the data population is normally distributed or not. In this study, the normality test was carried out by means of the *Liliefors test*. Researchers used the help of the *SPSS* version 23 programme to calculate data normality. The results of the *normality* test with the *Liliefors test* can be seen in the *Test of Normality output* on *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* at the *Sig* value. (significance). Data is declared normally distributed if the significance is greater than 0.05 (Priyatno, 2010: 71).

Based on the results of the data normality test for 42 items, all items have been distributed to 30 respondents, the significance value for the Windows Shoooping variable is 0.111 for the Learning Motivation variable of 0.121 and the Learning Achievement variable of 0.115, which means that these results state that the data has been distributed noermally and is suitable for further data testing.

b. Linearity Test

Linearity test is a test tool needed to determine the form of relationship that occurs between the variables being studied. This test is carried out to see the relationship between the two variables that have been studied whether there is a linear and significant relationship. The linearity test is a pre-requisite for using regression and correlation analysis.

Based on the results of the linearity test for 42 items, all items have been distributed to 30 respondents on the relationship between variable X and Y with a significance value greater than 0.05, which means that these results state that all variable X has a linear relationship with variable Y and is suitable for hypothesis testing.

3. Hypothesis Test Results

Regression analysis is a statistical technique useful for examining and modelling the relationship between variables. Multiple regression is often used to overcome regression analysis problems that result in the relationship of two or more independent variables (Ghozali, 2017).Ghozali, 2017). The independent variables in this study are Window Shopping Learning and Learning Motivation, while the dependent variable is Learning Achievement. This analysis method uses the *SPSS For Windows* programme. To assess the accuracy of the sample regression function in estimating the actual value, it can be measured from the statistical value of *Independent Samples (T Test)*, *One Way Anova Test*

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(F) and the value of the coefficient of determination.

a. Independent Samples Test (T Test)

This test is conducted to determine whether the independent variables of *Window Shopping* Learning Model (X1), and Learning Motivation (X2) individually affect the dependent variable, namely Learning Achievement (Y). Ghozali (2017) stated that the t statistical test shows how far the influence of one independent variable on the dependent variable with the assumption that the other independent variables are constant. This test is based on a significance level of 0.05.

Table 1. T Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	73.023	15.942		17.290	.000
	Windows Shopping	.550	.658	.630	8.110	.013
	Learning Motivation	.759	.644	.686	10.060	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement

Source: Secondary Data processed with SPSS, 2024.

Based on the results of the T test above, the following results are concluded:

1) The effect of Windows Shopping variables on Learning Achievement

The significance value on the relationship between the Windows Shopping variable and Learning Achievement was found to be $0.13 < 0.05$ and the tcount value

of $8.110 > t_{table} 0.683$, then these results concluded that there was a significant influence of the Windows Shopping variable on Learning Achievement. These results concluded that the research hypothesis which reads "There is an influence of the *Window Shopping learning* model on the learning achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan" is accepted.

2) The effect of Learning Motivation variables on Learning Achievement

The significance value in the relationship between the Learning Motivation variable and Learning Achievement was found to be $0.08 < 0.05$ and the tcount value of $10.060 > t_{table} 0.683$, so these results concluded that there was a significant influence of the Learning Motivation variable on Learning Achievement. These results concluded that the research hypothesis which reads "There is an influence of the Learning Motivation learning model on the learning achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan" is accepted.

b. One Way Anova Test (F Test)

F test, useful for testing the hypothesis of the regression coefficient (slope) simultaneously and ensuring that the selected model is feasible or not to interpret the effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable. This test is very important because if it does not pass the F test, the results of the t test are irrelevant (Ghozali, 2017).

Table 2. Simultaneous F Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	31.433	2	15.717	10.020	.034 ^b
	Residuals	415.934	27	15.405		
	Total	447.367	29			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement
b. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Motivation, Windows Shopping

The significance value in the relationship between the two variables *Windows Shopping* and Motivation to Learn on Learning Achievement was found to be $0.034 < 0.05$ and the value of Fcount of $10.020 > F_{table} 3, 34$, then these results concluded that there is a significant influence of the two variables *Windows Shopping* and Motivation to Learn on Learning Achievement. These results

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concluded that the research hypothesis which reads "There is an influence of the *Windows Shooping learning* model and Learning Motivation on the learning achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab.

Magetan" is accepted.

c. Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination essentially measures how far the model's ability to explain the variation in the independent variable on the dependent variable. In SPSS output, the coefficient of determination is located in the *Model Summary* table and is written *R Square*. However, for multiple linear regression, it is better to use the *adjusted R Square*, because it is adjusted for the number of independent variables used in the study. A small R^2 value means that the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation in the dependent variable is very limited. A value close to one means that the independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict variations in the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2017).Ghozali, 2017).

Table 3. Test Results of the Coefficient of Determination R2

<i>Model Summary^b</i>					
<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>Adjusted Square</i>	<i>R Std. Error of the Estimate</i>	<i>of Durbin-Watson</i>
1	.652 ^a	.770	.651	3.925	12.069
<i>a. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Motivation, Windows Shooping</i>					
<i>b. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement</i>					

Source: Secondary Data processed with SPSS, 2024.

Based on the results of the Coefficient of Determination test, the value of R^2 is 0.770 which means that the independent variables of the *Windows Shoopin learning* model (X1) and Learning Motivation (X2) have an influence of 77% on the Learning Achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan and the remaining 33% is influenced by other independent variables that are not the subject of discussion in this study.

DISCUSSION

1. The effect of Window Shopping learning model on Pancasila Education Learning Achievement in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan, Magetan Kab.

The significance value in the relationship between the *Windows Shopping* variable and Learning Achievement was found to be $0.13 < 0.05$ and the tcount value was $8.110 > t_{table} 0.683$, so these results concluded that there was a significant influence of the *Windows Shopping* variable on Learning Achievement. In the application of the *Window Shopping* type cooperative learning model, students learn together in groups to understand the learning material that can motivate students in improving writing skills. Students can learn actively and dynamically by displaying their work creatively, two people from each group guard their work (guarding the stand). Other group members visit the work of other groups (shopping) by giving comments and judgements. That way every student in the group can develop their creativity in making complex procedure texts. This kind of learning can create a fun, but effective situation according to the learning objectives to be achieved. This visiting activity is not just looking around, but students are asked to observe and record the work of other groups. (Istianingsih, 2018).

In the application of this learning model students walk around looking at the work of other groups. Students can learn actively and dynamically by displaying their work creatively, two people from each group guard their work (guarding the stand). Other group members visit the work of other groups (shopping) by giving comments and assessments so that each participant in the group can trigger their creativity so that the learning model that has been applied can create a pleasant situation, has been effective according to the learning objectives to be achieved, namely increasing learning achievement.

The results of this study are supported by research from Apriana (2020) which proves that the *Window Shopping* learning model can improve learning achievement in social studies subjects for students of SMP Negeri 1 Wanasaba. According to Hatimah (2022) from the results of his research, the *window shopping* learning model can make students feel they get attention and opportunities to express opinions, ideas, ideas and questions. Learners can work independently and in groups, and are able to be responsible for all individual and group tasks. The application of the *window shopping* type cooperative learning model has a positive influence, which can increase students' learning motivation so that both aspects can simultaneously improve students' learning

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achievement. Based on the theoretical and empirical studies above, there is a connection and influence of the application of *window shopping* learning model and learning motivation on student learning achievement.

In the data exposure of the distribution of *Windows Shooiping* variables to 30 respondents. The highest average value on this variable is indikator X1.4 which reads "The work of each student group is displayed on the classroom wall. This activity is considered a store opening in a mall and of course with problem solving as an exhibition" which is 1.90. While the indicator that has the highest standard deviation value is X1.10 which reads "Correction and feedback on student work to their group" which is 0.479 which means that this indicator has a wide variety of student answers. These results also illustrate that there is conformity from theory and findings in the field related to the learning process experienced by students in class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan there is a process of behavioural change by students as a result of interactions in their groups and based on observations in Class VII Pancasila Education subjects, it is known in theory that in the learning process through the *Windows Shooiping* learning model it increases students' interest in improving their understanding of the material rather than the learning model in the classroom using conventional learning, namely: lectures, questions and answers, and giving assignments, students only receive, hear, and record explanations conveyed by the teacher. This model encourages active participation of students in groups because it is based on group work by going around to see the work of other groups to broaden their horizons (Revianto, 2021).

2. The Effect of Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement of Pancasila Education of seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan, Magetan Kab.

The significance value in the relationship between the Learning Motivation variable and Learning Achievement was found to be $0.08 < 0.05$ and the tcount value of $10.060 > t_{table} 0.683$, so these results concluded that there was a significant influence of the Learning Motivation variable on Learning Achievement. The results of this study prove the theory that an important aspect that influences learning achievement is student motivation in the learning process (Soekamto and Winataputra, 1997). This is because learning motivation plays an important role in providing passion and enthusiasm in learning, so that students who have high motivation will have strong energy to learn. In addition, motivation will provide a clear direction in learning activities, so that students who have high motivation will have two solid wings to achieve a level of learning achievement (Winkel, 1996). The findings in this study can be explained that students who have learning motivation will have more influence on the level of capture of the subject matter presented by the teacher to carry out more effective learning tasks. The motivation that exists in students will be more developed, if they can receive learning well and have a high sense of curiosity.

In the data presentation of the distribution of Learning Motivation variables to 30 respondents. The highest average value on this variable is the X2.7 and X2.10 indicators which read "If the teacher gives praise for my success in solving problems, then I become even more eager to solve other problems" and "I am happy with this learning because it is interesting and not boring" which is 3.57. While the indicator that has the highest standard deviation value is X2.1 which is written "I try to do my assignments on time" which is 0.887 which means that this indicator has a wide variety of student answers. These results illustrate that in the learning process, teachers must increase learning motivation to students by giving praise during assessment and continuing to improve the creation of an interesting learning atmosphere so that it is not boring.

3. The Effect of Window Shopping Learning Model and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement of Pancasila Education at SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan, seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan, Magetan Kab.

The significance value in the relationship between the two variables *Windows Shooiping* and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement was found to be $0.034 < 0.05$ and the Fcount value of $10.020 > F_{table} 3, 34$, so these results concluded that there was a significant influence of the two variables *Windows Shooiping* and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement. As for the test results of the Coefficient of Determination, the value of R^2 is 0.770 which means that the independent variables of *Windows Shooipin* learning model (X1) and Learning Motivation (X2) have an influence of 77% on the Learning Achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan and the remaining 33% is influenced by other independent variables that are not the subject of discussion in this study.

The results of this study support the findings of Hatimah (2022) from the results of his research, that the *window shopping* learning model can make students feel that they get attention and opportunities to express opinions, ideas, ideas and questions. Learners can work independently and in groups, and are able to take responsibility for all individual and group tasks. The application of the *window shopping* type cooperative learning model has a positive influence, which can increase students' learning motivation so that both aspects can simultaneously improve students' learning achievement. Based on the theoretical and empirical studies above, there is a connection and influence of the application of *window shopping* learning model and learning motivation on student learning achievement.

In the data presentation of the distribution of Learning Achievement variables to 30 respondents. The highest average value on this variable is the Y20 indicator which is written "Name the religions, places of worship, and holy books and holidays in Indonesia!"

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which is 9.33. While the indicator that has the highest standard deviation value is Y.6 which reads "Ethnic groups in Indonesia usually have their own organisations. The negative impact of tribal-based organisations is:" which is 9.33 which means that this indicator has a wide variety of student answers.

CONCLUSION

After going through the results of the analysis and discussion, the results of this study concluded that the significance value in the relationship between the Windows Shopping variable on Learning Achievement was obtained at $0.13 < 0.05$ and the tcount value of $8.110 > t$ table 0.683, then this result concluded that there was a significant influence of the Windows Shopping variable on Learning Achievement. The significance value in the relationship between the Learning Motivation variable and Learning Achievement was found to be $0.08 < 0.05$ and the tcount value of $10.060 > t$ table 0.683, so this result concluded that there was a significant effect of the Learning Motivation variable on Learning Achievement. The significance value in the relationship between the two variables Windows Shopping and

Motivation to Learn was found to be $0.034 < 0.05$ and the Fcount value of $10.020 > F$ table 3.34, so this result concluded that there was a significant influence of the two variables Windows Shopping and Motivation to Learn on Learning Achievement. Based on the test results of the Coefficient of Determination obtained R^2 value of 0.770 which means that the independent variable Windows Shopping learning model (X1) and Learning Motivation (X2) has an influence of 77% on the Learning Achievement of Pancasila Education class VII SMP Negeri 1 Plaosan Kab. Magetan and the remaining 33% is influenced by other independent variables that are not the subject of discussion in this study.

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